

Effect of different urea materials on rice yield.

N source	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	1978	1979	1980	1981	Mean
Control	3.65	2.43	3.39	1.95	2.85
Urea 3 split	5.90	5.95	5.21	5.53	5.65
SCU	6.51	6.32	6.00	6.61	6.36
USG	5.64	3.55	4.06	2.99	4.06
Lac-coated urea	5.93	5.10	—	4.99	5.33
Neem-cake-coated urea	5.77	4.41	5.09	4.54	4.96
Urea all at transplanting	5.27	4.39	4.90	—	4.85
CD .05	—	0.66	0.85	0.31	—

K/ha was applied at last puddling.

Results (see table) showed that SCU, followed by split application of prilled urea, produced significantly superior grain yields. A similar trend was reflected in progressive dry matter accumulation and total N-uptake (Fig. 1, 2). USG gave the lowest biomass accumulation and N uptake. The rapid percolation rate and 10 cm placement may have caused USG to leach beyond the rice rooting zone. SCU, because of controlled release, yielded higher than prilled urea. □

1. Dry matter accumulation by rice as affected by different N sources applied at 120 kg N/ha.

2. Rice uptake of N from different sources applied at 120 kg N/ha.

Effect of organic residues on pulling force of rice seedlings

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High yielding rice varieties are the most important kharif (wet season) cereal crop in Punjab. Transplanted rice nurseries are grown on small flat beds. Seeds are broadcast after the seedbed is thoroughly wetted and puddled. Seedlings are difficult to pull from flat beds and often are broken. We studied soil amendments to reduce pulling force.

Replicated experiments were con-

ducted in 2- x 2-m plots in sandy loam at Ludhiana and in silt loam at Gurdaspur. The Ludhiana experiments were conducted for 2 years. Studies at Gurdaspur were for 1 year. Treatments are described in the table. Pulling force was measured on 40-day-old seedlings and expressed as pulling force index (PFI), a nondimensional parameter.

Results showed that the pulling force was significantly higher in puddled seedbeds than in raised seedbeds, irrespective of soil type. PFI in raised seedbeds was 30 in sandy loam and 84 in silt loam. It increased to 70 and 175 in puddled seedbeds.

Pulling force was significantly af-

Effect of different organic residues on PFI of rice nurseries in sandy loam and silt loam, Punjab, Indian.^a

Treatment ^b	PFI	
	Sandy loam	Silt loam
Raised bed (control)	30 ^d	84 ^d
Puddled (control)	70 ^a	175 ^a
15 t FYM/ha, puddled	56 ^b	123 ^c
30 t FYM/ha, puddled	50 ^b	120 ^c
4 t rice husk/ha, puddled	57 ^b	135 ^b
8 t rice husk/ha, puddled	39 ^c	122 ^c

^aIn a column, figures with similar letters do not differ significantly. ^b FYM = farmyard manure.

ected by organic residue treatments. Highest PFI values (70 and 175) were recorded in the controls. PFI was de-

creased when organic residues were added, but results of different organic residue treatments, except 8 t rice husk/ha, did not differ significantly. Adding rice husk reduced PFI to almost half that of

the sandy loam control. In silt loam, adding 4 t rice husk/ha was not as effective as adding farmyard manure and 8 t rice husk/ha.

Results indicate that applying farm-

yard manure or rice husk to nursery beds helped reduce seedling pulling force. However, seedbeds with rice husk and other low nitrogenous residues may need additional nitrogen. □

Effect of rice hulls applied to rice fields

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Rice hull at 20 t/ha was spread over a rice field about 1 week before planting, and the field was plowed, manured, and puddled. The operations significantly improved rice growth and yield and the soil texture, compared to the control (see table).

Data show that rice hulls have no allelopathic effect on rice, although rice straw has some such effect before decay. The increase in silica content in both plant and soil suggests that tolerance for blast disease can be improved.

Effect of 20 t rice hull on rice growth and yield, Taiwan, 1980 winter.^a

Attribute	Rice hull applied	Control
Grain yield (t/ha)	8.2	7.2
Panicles (no./m ²)	399	377
Single panicle wt (g)	2.6	2.2
Test wt (g/1000 grains)	26	24
Leaf silica content (%)	14	5
Soil redox potential (mv)	-169	-150
Exchangeable K in soil (ppm)	64	42
Silica in soil (ppm)	212	112
Organic matter in soil (%)	2.2	2.0

^a Variety = Tainung 65.

Nitrogen fertilization in transplanted rice

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In the 1981 monsoon season we evaluated the efficiency of urea, sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea supergranules (USG), and lac-coated urea (LCU) at 0, 29, 58, 87, and 116 kg N/ha on flooded transplanted rice in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. Soil in the field was a silty clay loam Alfisol with pH 5.8, 0.73% organic carbon, 628.19 kg available N/ha, 10.8 kg available P/ha, and 144.78 kg available K/ha. Cation exchange capacity was 17.2 meq/100 g. At puddling, all plots received 18 kg P as single superphosphate (16% P₂O₅) and 33 kg P/ha as muriate of potash (60% K₂O).

Grain yield increased significantly and consistently as nitrogen level increased up to 87 kg N/ha. USG produced significantly higher grain yield than three equal splits of ordinary urea (at transplanting, maximum tillering, and panicle initiation) and other nitrogen sources. SCU was not a better nitrogen source for flooded rice in acidic soil.

Nitrogen use was 1.8 times more efficient than the best split application when applied as USG. Split application of urea had lowest efficiency at all but at 116 kg N/ha (see table). □

Effect of N levels and sources on rice yield and N use efficiency at Palampur, India.

N level (kg/ha)	N source ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	N use efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
0 (control)	None	2.2	-
	Urea	3.6	45.5
	SCU	3.8	55.1
	USG	4.6	82.3
	LCU	3.7	49.8
58	Urea	4.6	40.6
	SCU	4.8	43.6
	USG	5.4	53.8
	LCU	5.2	51.1
87	Urea	5.4	36.4
	SCU	5.5	37.8
	USG	6.0	42.9
	LCU	5.6	38.4
116	Urea	5.5	28.3
	SCU	5.2	25.8
	USG	5.9	31.4
	LCU	5.5	27.7
		SEm ±	CD 5%
For N levels		0.28	0.81
For sources		0.28	0.81
For interaction		0.56	1.62

^a SCU = sulfur-coated urea, USG = urea supergranules, LCU = lac-coated urea.

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Effect of source and timings of nitrogen fertilizer application on rice grain yield in heavy sodic soil

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Fertilizer requirements and efficiency in sodic soil differ from those in normal soil.

We studied the efficiency of different N fertilizers applied at different growth stages on the yield of high yielding, salt-tolerant dwarf variety CSR4 during 2 consecutive years in virgin sodic soil at the Barwaha experiment station (W. Nimar district, Madhya Pradesh).

No soil amendment was applied in the replicated field experiment. In both years 150 kg N in different forms, 33 kg K/ha were applied to all plots (Table 1).

Fifty percent N was applied basally by broadcasting and incorporation on puddled soil with standing water before transplanting, and 50% was topdressed in one or two applications.

Soil samples were collected from the submerged field at 4 places in each 4- × 6-m plot. Electrical conductivity (EC) and pH were measured after drying, grinding, and sieving. Cation exchange capacity (CEC) and exchangeable sodium